

CitySCAPE

BRAND Guidelines

Table of Contents

CitySCAPE logo

3

Logo Variations

5

Color pallet guide

7

logo usage

8

Logo improper use

9

Social media usage

10

Usage in a colour background

11

Brand typography

12

Brand Logo

The idea behind

Logo Elements

Colors

The CitySCAPE logo uses two colors: blue and cyan

Blue = Blue represents both the sky and the sea and for that reason is commonly used in the maritime sector. Since the project focusing on enhancing SSS and the respective ports' capacity, the color blue could not but predominate the CitySCAPE graphical ID.

cyan = Cyan is made by mixing the colours green and blue light. It is commonly used with blue, as a secondary colour, to provide some light in the designs. In CitySCAPE logo it was also used as a variation of green, which is by definition the symbol of ecology, to represent the efforts of the project to develop solutions that will also reduce the environmental footprint for SSS services and port areas compared to other modes.

Logo Variations

Positive Format (Primary Format)

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. In cases where this is not feasible, the versions on page 6 are available for usage.

Logo Variations

a) Negative Format:

This format of the CitySCAPE logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

b) BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

Color Pallette

MAIN COLORS

CMYK = C70 M15 Y0 K0
RGB = R0 G174 B239
#00aeef

CMYK = C80 M80 Y0 K0
RGB = R82 G79 B161
#524fa1

ADDITIONAL COLORS

CMYK = C28 M82 Y0 K0
RGB = R255 G0 B255
#ff00ff

CMYK = C35 M90 Y0 K0
RGB = R190 G45 B180
#be2db4

CMYK = C60 M100 Y30 K420
RGB = R111 G23 B97
#6f1761

CMYK = C0 M30 Y70 K0
RGB = R49 G137 B197
#3189c5

MAIN and ADDITIONAL COLORS

CMYK colors are used in printing material
RGB colors are used on web applications

Additional color pallette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets e.t.c. in case you need a small touch of color contrast. These colors cannot replace main color pallette or logotype official colors

Logo Usage

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the CitySCAPE logotype. Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the CitySCAPE logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

To make sure the logo is always clear and legible, a minimum size requirement was determined. However, when using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

LOGOTYPE PRINT minimum size
35 mm W X 17,5 mm H

LOGOTYPE SCREEN minimum size
180 px W | 86 px H

Logo Improper use

Display the CitySCAPE logo only in the formats that are specified in this guide. The CitySCAPE logo may not appear in any other colors than the already specified in page 7 of this guide.

Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, alter or distort the CitySCAPE logo in any way.

Do not combine the CitySCAPE logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

Logo usage on social media

Logo use on social media: the logo should be used in a white background.

Logo usage on backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, color or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background.

The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

Typography brand

Must be always used to all communications material and in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the CitySCAPE website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given typeface with others should not be done under any circumstances.

Montserrat fonts family

Regular ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Regular Italic
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light Italic *ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ*
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bold **ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ**
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bold Italic ***ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ***
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Typography brand

1) For MS templates and publications

HEADING 1
Calibri bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2
Calibri bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3
Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4
Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

Body text
Calibri-Regular, 11pt, black colors

2) For Website and other web-applications

HEADING 1
Calibri bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2
Calibri bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3
Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4
Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text
Calibri-Regular, 11pt, black colors

3) For leaflets and other material

HEADING 1
Calibri bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2
Calibri bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3
Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37
G60 B126)

HEADING 4
Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

Body text
Calibri-Regular, 11pt, black colors

CitySCAPE

BRAND

Guidelines